

ADOPTION OF “REFLECTION” MODEL FOR REFLECTIVE PRACTICE IN TEAMWORK AND DEVELOPING PROFESSIONAL INTERPERSONAL SKILLS

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Abstract

Given the diverse contexts and cultures in global and international business, reflective practice in teaching and learning has become critically important for professional courses and postgraduate degree programs. While reflection in teaching and learning refers to a serious deliberation about students' learning experience, reflective practice suggests the ability to reflect on students' actions and behaviours in cross-cultural teamwork and their engagement in continuous learning experiences in global and international business. This paper presents a novel conceptual and applied model that has been developed and used over the years collaboratively with teachers, students, quality assurance experts, and inputs from feedback processes that are associated with an accredited postgraduate degree programs' learning and teaching experience. The approach involves actively analysing students' and teachers' experiences and actions to help both parties to learn and apply cross-cultural teamwork and professional interpersonal concepts and skills in cross-cultural scenarios. The result of adapting this process over three years indicates the emergence of ten steps cyclical model that consists of reviewing, experiencing, falsifying, learning, evidence-based reflection, critical reflection, testing, integrating, opportunity utilisation, and new strategies. The acronym of these steps and the models is named as REFLECTION model. While the elements in the model are conceptually supported by several reflective and experiential learning theories, it emphasises the power of integration and collaborative reflection as critical novel features. Further, the model also contributes to the knowledge enhancement in multidisciplinary perspective on reflective practice. Several limitations and suggestions for continuous development in reflective practice are also presented.

Keywords: Reflective practices; Teaching and learning; Teamwork; International Business

1. INTRODUCTION

This paper presents an introduction to and adoption of a new model for reflective practice, which is named as REFLECTION model. Conceptually, reflective practice allows practitioners and learners to review, define, refine, expand, adapt, teach, adopt, and apply teaching and learning experiences for the purpose of teaching and coaching, personal development, and wider organisational development (Lawrence-Wilkes & Ashmore 2014). Despite the undeniable significance of reflection and reflective practice in the context of human experience, there exists a gap in our understanding of how to effectively connect and leverage this powerful phenomenon, particularly within the realms of education and individual and professional development. Thus, the notion of reflection and reflective practice have become influential in shaping the mindset and implementation of management education and development (Reynolds 2011).

The present paper intends to respond to two practical questions associated with the above-mentioned knowledge and practice gap in teaching and learning. First, how can we integrate different aspects and perspectives of the process of reflective practice? Second, how can instructors and students collaborate within an appropriate reflective model? Thus, this paper aims to suggest an integrated and collaborative model for reflective practice that can be used by students and teachers simultaneously.

In view of this pressing need, our research aims to fill the knowledge gap concerning the practical implications of reflection and reflective practice. We intend to investigate how the enchanting phenomenon of reflection can be utilised as a potent instrument in education, teamwork, and professional growth. By delving deeper into the multifarious aspects of reflection, we expect to develop a comprehensive framework that can assist both educators and students in realising its transformative potential. Through a comprehensive review of the existing literature and empirical investigations, our research aims to not only shed light on the significance of reflection but also provide actionable insights into its effective incorporation into educational curricula and professional development programmes. Thus, the motivation behind this study stems from the conviction that a deeper understanding of reflection can facilitate more efficient learning processes and foster the development of crucial skills necessary for individual and professional development.

2. THEORIES AND CONCEPTUAL MODELS

A range of theories, models, as well as principles of reflective practice is used in this paper. While reflective theory supposes facts, models help us assess reflective practices in learning and teaching. The principles represent values, beliefs, and styles of reflective practice. As it covers all these three aspects to some extent, the Kolb's (1984) learning cycle model provides a good foundation for many reflective theories and models. The Kolb's model works on four stage cycles such as concrete experience, reflective observation, abstract conceptualisation, and active experimentation. Associated with these are four kinds of definitions of the learning styles such as diverging, assimilating, converging, and accommodating. While recognising a few stages, including the actual experience stage, we have referred to the Kolb model several times in our discussion section.

Gibbs (1988) reflective learning model consists of six stages: Description, Feelings, Evaluation, Analysis, Conclusion, and Action plan. Although it is a bit more complex than Kolb's (1984) model, having multiple stages seems to guide us in reassuring the reflection. As discussed in the discussion section of this paper, some stages, such as description, evaluation, analysis, and action plan, are closely associated with our REFLECTION model.

Donald Schon (1991) defined reflective practice as the ability to reflect on one's actions to engage in continuous learning. He stresses the need for reflection in action, in addition to reflection on action, and provides an additional element by distinguishing between reflection during and after the event. Thus, Schon is best known for his work on the reflective practitioner, in which he formulated a new epistemology of practice founded on knowing-in-action and reflection-in-action, a theory that has had considerable impact. It is, therefore, useful for practitioners to take account of this distinction during our own reflective practice. For example, reflection-in-action takes place in the classroom (Ramage, 2017). This is the style of reflection when the teacher observes what is taking place at the moment (e.g., in-class teamwork activities) or as the instruction or activities are taking place (Mermelstein, 2018).

Leering (2017) defines an integrated reflective practitioner as "a professional" who integrates theory and practice, critically reflects on practice (what one does), and theory (what one knows), and what one believes as a self-directed life-long learner, and then take actions based on that reflection to improve their practice. This kind of professional recognises the power of reflecting collectively, learning from others and other disciplines, to enhance professional services, increase professional knowledge, ensure rigour about one's reflections, and generate new insights and interdisciplinary knowledge." (pp.49-50). The following section discusses the method we have adopted in this study to fill the identified knowledge gap.

3. METHOD IN BRIEF

The research about theories, principles, and models of reflective practice is conducted. A few theories directly related to our model are selected to produce the reflective activities. The justification for reasons for chosen approach is offered with evidence in the discussion section. Our approach is based on the recognition of several principles. First, reflection is both a personal and a collective process, and everyone will work towards it differently. Second, we have taken three years to try different approaches until we find the one that we have found and presented in this paper- the REFLECTION model. Third, we may find that as time goes on and we develop further as reflective practitioners, we might find different methods and models

that suit our changing circumstances.

Having recognised these principles, our approach to the development of the model is integrative and collaborative as a case study method. It consists of sharing some key elements in the collaborative, reflective process, which includes, subject learning outcomes, assessment types, teaching practices, making criteria and rubrics, student feedback, and self-reflection and experience on the subject delivery and management for over three years. For ethical reasons, we do not share any identity or specific piece of data in this paper, but abstract, summarised, published, and self-reflective data.

Our case study consists of instructors and postgraduate students whose coursework requires them to engage in teamwork and developing professional interpersonal skills. In addition to various other aspects of teaching and learning activities, they have been provided with the opportunity to engage in in-class teamwork activities (5 Weeks) and teamwork-based assessments, which consist of team presentations and business reports (4 Weeks). During the course, the instructors use all three specified styles: reflect-in, reflect-on, and reflect-for, while students perform the said in-class and teamwork activities. While individual student's teamwork engagement is assessed by peer team members, the outputs produced by teams are evaluated by the instructor. The marking rubrics for students' teamwork consist of indicators associated with seven stages (4 to 10) of the REFLECTION model (Figure 1).

Figure 1: The Model Developed and Adopted

Assumptions of the development and execution of the REFLECTION model:

The following assumptions are relevant to the development and execution of this reflective practice model.

1. The order doesn't imply that steps should be followed in a particular way. For example, in your context, you may not start with reviewing but experiencing or learning.
2. The steps work in a cyclical process.
3. The process is continuous.
4. The model may not apply in every single situation.

4. DISCUSSION

The REFLECTION model is a systematic and iterative approach that provides individuals with a framework consisting of ten crucial elements. Each stage assumes a pivotal function in the cultivation of cross-cultural proficiency. The model under consideration emphasises the importance of actively reviewing one's experiences, engaging in critical reflection on one's actions, and consistently adapting and enhancing cross-cultural teamwork skills by implementing new techniques. By employing this paradigm, individuals better understand their strengths and shortcomings, thereby boosting their capacity to function effectively in cross-cultural contexts. The primary objective of introducing the REFLECTION model is to enhance cross-cultural

collaboration and teamwork. This methodology aims to facilitate the integration of theoretical knowledge and practical application by actively involving students and teachers in their experiences and actions. By employing a methodology rooted in evidence-based analysis and continuous learning, this approach presents a hopeful strategy for equipping individuals with the requisite abilities to flourish in an ever more heterogeneous global society. Thus, this study significantly contributes to the field of cross-cultural education and offers valuable insights into the wider context of professional development and interpersonal skills. The following section discusses the meanings and implications of each of the ten stages of the REFLECTION model.

4.1. Reviewing

Reflective practice starts with reviewing a given situation to understand where we are now in the reflection process. For many educators, it might be a subject outline, program and subject level learning outcomes, current assignments, current reflective practices, existing marking criteria and rubrics, feedback information from stakeholders, etc. When you compare this information with your knowledge and experience and the expectations of and feedback from stakeholders, you might find gaps to fill or address, which you can plan from the next stage of the reflective process onwards. This step is consistent with the meaning of "Description" element of the Gibbs (1988) model, which emphasises making sense of the situation and relevant parties' experience. It allows us and students to analyse and evaluate the positive and negative aspects of their experience and what they could have done differently.

4.2. Experiencing/ Experimenting

By definition, a reflective practice consists of doing or applying what teachers have taught, or students have been taught. As such experiencing or experimenting is an essential element of the reflective cycle. Conceptually, this idea is consistent with the concepts such as "learning by doing" and "hands on experience", which are consistent with Kolb's (1984) experiential learning theory. In the teacher-student relationship, this element is relevant to both parties. For example, educators can think of various ways and means as alternative opportunities to be provided for students in their delivery and assessment tasks, such as real-world case studies, teamwork activities, work-integrated learning, classroom, or lab activities, etc. When these outcomes are linked to subject learning outcomes, students are formally required to engage in these experiential activities. In addition, current generations are intrinsically motivated to gain practical experience in their learning.

4.3. Falsifying

This simply means altering, modifying, and fabricating. As a result of executing the above step 1(Reviewing) and Step 2 (Experiencing), it is a natural and essential requirement to take corrective actions and ensure continuous and lifelong learning. Therefore, altering, modifying, changing, replacing, improving, etc., are some of the ways and means of falsifying previous teaching and learning practices. Thus, this is associated with redesigning subject and course learning outcomes, introducing new content, redesigning assessment tasks, new classroom activities, new work environments, etc. The invention and adoption of this REFLECTION model itself is another example of falsification. Within this model, the introduction of new elements such as "Integration" is another example.

Further, the results of self-learning, student feedback, and the need for improving performance are some common inputs. In international business and cross-cultural scenarios, students cannot depend on their previous practices when they go to a new country or interact with culturally diverse teams. Conceptually, this is a key requirement for engaging in the "Reflect-in" style in practice (Farrells, 2012). Further, Schon (1991) emphasises that as professionals practice rigorously technical problem-solving based on specialised scientific knowledge, instrumental adjustments of means to end are required in practice.

4.4. Learning

This is the basic element of any model of learning, experiential learning, or reflection practice. It simply means changing or adapting to new knowledge, skills, attitudes, behaviours, practices, or any target outcome of the learning process. Simply, for example, when enquired from students about their learning in teamwork, they indicated that they have learned not only new theories and models, but also how to use them in practice while engaging in teamwork. On the one hand, we cannot talk about any reflective practice without having the "learning" element, and the reflective practice is essential for effective and continuous learning, on the other. Thus, the learning and reflective practices are reciprocally related. Conceptually, Kolb's (1984) experiential learning somewhat addresses this link. Schon's (1991) and Farrells's (2012) styles

of “Reflection-in” are associated with learning in practice or by doing, which may be different from learning previously established theories and practices. It is also important to note that learning can occur in many other ways and means also (e.g., observing, enquiring, reading, etc.).

4.5. Evidence-Based Reflection

Evidence-based refers to any concept or strategy derived from or informed by objective evidence (Petty, 2006; De Vera Barrido, 2005). Evidence-based practice and reflection are both processes that share very similar aims and procedures (Mantzoukas, 2008). Using evidence through examples of personal experiences and thoughts, often integrated with theoretical literature and concepts, is very relevant to teamwork and interpersonal skills development. In teacher-student relationships, evidence-based reflection is equally important for both parties. For example, different students in the same team accumulate different evidence gathered through their levels and engagement areas, which also depend on their strengths and weaknesses. Therefore, it maintains the firsthand practitioner perspective and integrity of the reflective process. For teachers, an educational strategy is evidence-based, data-based, or research-based. They use objective evidence to inform the design of an academic program or guide the modification of instructional techniques and assessments.

4.6. Critical Reflection

The need for and the idea of critical reflection is emphasised in several reflective models (Gibbs, 1988; De Vera Barrido, 2005; Leering, 2017). For example, evidence-based reflective practice provides a basis for critical reflection (De Vera Barrido, 2005). In the education environment, some of the most commonly used objective evidence for critical reflection include educational research or metrics of school, teacher’s experience, and student performance. One of the key principles of a critical reflection is that it should be relevant to the context or contextualised (Eyler et al. 1996). This principle is very much applicable to cross-cultural teams, in which the participants are taught and required to be critical when selecting teamwork practices appropriate to cultures of different countries and organisations. The same principle is applicable when they adapt to the requirements of different countries, cultures, and teams.

4.7. Testing

One way of testing students’ learning experience is the adoption of reflective practice in assessment tasks. Gibbs’ (1988) “evaluation” practice and Farrell’s (2012) “Reflection-for” styles are directly associated with the testing element of our REFLECTION model. For example, we have proposed reflection for the purpose of testing students’ learning experience in teamwork and developing professional interpersonal relationships and for the assurance of learning outcomes (AOL) in cross-cultural management courses. The outcome of testing is used as input to the “Review” and “New Strategy” development functions of our cyclical model. At organisational level, the outcome of testing is also used as an indicator of teaching effectiveness.

4.8. Integration

One of the key elements of Leering (2017) model is “Reflection on Integration”. On the question of integration of what, Leering (2017) emphasised reflection on at least three elements: what one knows (theory), what one does (practice), and what one believes. For example, in cross-cultural teamwork, we believe in the power of integrating different topics, such as leadership, communication, negotiations and conflict resolution, CQ, etc., when they engage in effective teamwork. Eyler et al. (1996) state that a good reflection is “connected”. We also emphasised the power of integrating teachers’ and students’ reflection, which is one of the unique features of our REFLECTION model. In addition, we emphasise the need for integrating different disciplines in international business strategy subjects and integrating multidisciplinary knowledge.

4.9. Opportunity Utilisation

Reflective practice involves action or doing for which there should be opportunities. While opportunity creation in teaching and learning is believed to be an instructor’s responsibility, utilisation of such opportunities to apply subject knowledge is students’ responsibility. This also represents the “Reflect-on” style of Farrell’s (2012) framework. Thus, reflection on the opportunity given to practice can be considered a key requirement of reflective practice. Without practising or engaging, one cannot reflect on practice effectively (Schon, 1991). In cross-cultural management courses, students are provided with opportunities to engage in teamwork as classroom activities and teamwork-based assignments. The effectiveness of utilising these opportunities determines the effectiveness of their reflection on the learning experience.

4.10. New Strategies

Adopting new strategies is a key requirement for improvement and continuous as well as lifelong learning (Gibbs, 1988). According to Eyler et al. (1996), a good reflection is “continuous”. In addition to students’ experience and changing contexts in practising, feedback from their instructors also plays a critical role in formulating new strategies. For an instructor, the “reflection-for” style focuses on utilising the information gathered through various sources to create opportunities to improve the instruction or activity for future deliveries. According to Leering (2017), professionals who integrate theory, practice, and what they believe as self-directed life-long learners take actions based on their reflection to improve their practice. This kind of professional generates new insights and enhances professional services. In cross-cultural teamwork, students’ learning experience guides them to think in advance about appropriate adaptation strategies for new cross-cultural contexts.

The discussion above reveals that the traditional forms of education and training frequently prove insufficient in adequately equipping individuals to tackle some integration, collaborative and flexibility issues discussed in this paper (Le et al. 2018). In order to rectify this deficiency, the REFLECTION model presents a comprehensive resolution. By integrating academic knowledge, practical experiences, and reflective practices, the proposed model aims to equip both students and teachers with the necessary skills to effectively traverse the intricate dynamics of cross-cultural encounters.

5. CONCLUSION

This paper introduced and adopted the REFLECTION model developed by accumulating theories, practices, and individual learning experiences and beliefs of instructors and students of a postgraduate degree program over three years. As discussed in the previous section, each word of the REFLECTION term represents an active meaning for each stage of the reflective process. The model offers a comprehensive view of reflective practice by emphasising flexibility in the order of execution and the power of integration and collective reflection. In particular, it integrates several aspects of reflective practice covering both students’ and instructors’ perspectives using Reflect-in, Reflect-on, and Reflect-for styles; Reflect on theory, Reflect on practice, and reflect on individual learner/practitioner believes; integration of different topics of the same subject to improve teamwork performance and integrating knowledge and experience of different disciplines to make organisational level decisions, and the power of collaborative reflections. For the benefits of the adoption and execution of individual stages, the model offers several assumptions.

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